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“AT THE EDGE OF A PATIENT’S BREATH”

Loss and grief cuts through my chest,
Like a drilling machine that will never rest.
I stand with emergent but shaking cold feet,
As i witness a patient catch his breath.

In the cold room linger anxiety and fear,
The feeling of uncertainty is loud and clear.
These are my lived experiences, raw and real,
Lessons no lecture could reveal.

I learn the role of healthcare is not to cure alone,
But to conquer the emotion, to soften the unknown.
Through silent prayers and steady breath,
I craft my coping mechanisms in the face of death.

A profound sense of responsibility I bear,
In every illness, in every prayer.
The aching challenges in communication,
Between prognosis and expectation.

My emotional responses rise and fall,
A quiet tear fall in an empty hall.
In each diagnosis, I find professional growth,
In sorrow, an unspoken oath.

